

COMPOSITES OF MgB₂ – RARE-EARTH-OXIDES: FABRICATION BY SPARK PLASMA SINTERING AND FUNCTIONAL PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

Dense MgB₂ samples with La₂O₃ addition were obtained by spark plasma sintering. We used two different La₂O₃ raw powders showing different particle sizes and shapes. The as-obtained composite samples have significant differences in microstructure and Vickers hardness. A deposited phosphate layer was obtained by immersing the samples in PBS, and drying. Formation of phosphate needles, gathered in bouquets, show a possible bioactive behavior of MgB₂.

1 INTRODUCTION

Magnesium diboride (MgB₂) was synthesized for the first time in 1953 [1], but only after 2001 gain a huge scientific interest, when its superconducting properties were discovered [2]. As a superconducting material, MgB₂ is prized for: (i) it is a compound with a simple layered hexagonal crystal structure achieving the highest critical temperature T_c for a simple binary superconductor of ~ 39 K, (ii) the coherence length ξ is relatively large, of ~10 nm [3], (iii) it has a two-band electronic structure, (iv) it can be used at 20 K, cooled by cryocoolers, (v) it is a light-weight material (2.63 g/cm³) recommended for fabrication of portable/small devices, (vi) it is relatively stable, non-toxic, available and cheap material, and (vii) it can be easily manufactured into large parts with different shapes. Some of the presented characteristics make MgB₂ of interest for other applications. Among them, points (v-vii) are potentially appealing for bio medical applications.

Different additives are added to MgB₂ to tune superconducting properties [4, 5]. They are sources of carbon for the substitution of boron into the crystal lattice of MgB₂, or they generate MgB₂-based composites. In the second case new phases may occur if the additive is reacting with MgB₂. The resulting microstructures will depend not only on the additive nature, but also on the morphology features of the additive as a raw powder [6]. Processing technology is also important. Processing technologies of MgB₂ are of *in situ* or *ex situ* types. In the *in situ* approach, Mg and B are used, while for the *ex-situ* route the already formed MgB₂ is used. In our work we applied the *ex-situ* spark plasma sintering (SPS). In SPS, heating is realized through a pulsed current supplied on the punches-mold-sample system. During SPS heating also a uniaxial pressure is applied on the powder sample. The final material has a high bulk density, above 90 % [7].

Recently, based on degradability of MgB₂ in aqueous solution we proposed MgB₂ added with RE₂O₃ (RE = rare earth element) as a biodegradable material with potential for medical applications [8, 9]. The biodegradability is a very important issue when we consider the surgical applications [10]. Search of new materials and practical solutions providing improved properties for different biomedical materials including of those based on Mg is at present of much interest [11]. Magnesium-based materials are important due to their low density, good mechanical properties, and biodegradability. At the same time, there are some negative issues, such as the high corrosion rate. The consequence is a rapid decrease of the mechanical properties. Other side effects are the hydrogen release (1 L per 1 g of Mg) and high pH values, up to 11 for pure Mg in solution [12, 13]. One solution is to cover the bulk

material with a bioactive coating material, e.g. with calcium – phosphate (Ca-P) or hydroxyapatite (HA). The respective coatings are promoting a better interface between an orthopedic implant and bone tissue. There are various methods for Ca-P or HA deposition. One of them consists simply in immersing the samples in the simulated body fluid (SBF) [14-17]. This method is also conventionally used for a rapid *in vitro* testing of the bioactivity of a material envisioned to be in contact with bones. However, false positive or negative results may occur [15]. The SBF immersion method requires a certain methodology to follow: it is somehow a time consuming test, and much care is necessary to avoid the precipitation of the apatite in solution, by homogeneous nucleation, and the bacteria contamination [15-17]. The immersed samples into SBF will induce heterogeneous nucleation on their surface, by several mechanisms, such as [15] (i) providing apatite nuclei, (ii) low sample surface/apatite interfacial energy or (iii) changing the local solution supersaturation favorable to apatite precipitation. Similar to bioglass [15], MgB₂ increases the local pH of solution with the possible consequence of promoting an accelerated apatite nucleation. Considering that other solutions can also promote Ca-P or apatite formation [15], in this work we proposed Phosphate Buffer Saline (PBS), as a simplified deposition solution. One main advantage is that PBS can be acquired as a powder or as a ready standard prepared solution. Thus, the reproducibility of the tests, due to the solution quality, is increased.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

Pristine MgB₂, micro-La₂O₃ and nano-La₂O₃-added MgB₂ with composition (MgB₂)_{0.975}(LaO_{1.5})_{0.025} were produced by Spark Plasma Sintering (SPS). Conventionally, “nano” denotes samples with added powder of La₂O₃ with an average particle size lower than 100 nm, and “micro” - higher than 100 nm (Fig. 1, Table 1). The MgB₂ and the La₂O₃ addition powders (Table 1) were manually mixed in an agate mortar. Powder mixtures were loaded into a 2 cm diameter graphite die and processed by SPS (FCT Systeme GmbH – HP D 5, Germany) at 1150 °C for 3 minutes, under a uniaxial pressure of 95 MPa applied on the punches of the graphite die. More details about fabrication by SPS are presented in ref. [18].

Apparent densities (ρ_a) of the sintered samples (Table 2) were measured by Archimedes method using a KERN ALT 220-4M density balance.

The structural characterization was performed by X-ray diffraction technique (XRD, Bruker-AXS D8 ADVANCE, $\lambda_{\text{CuK}\alpha} = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). Crystallite size from the XRD patterns was determined according to Williamson-Hall method [19].

Scanning electron microscopy images (SEM-EDS) were taken with Zeiss EVO50 on fresh surfaces of the fractured samples and on polished sample surfaces before and after immersion test in PBS.

Vickers hardness (HV) was measured (CV-400DTS Micro Hardness Tester) for different loadings on polished surfaces. We applied the standard procedure according to ASTM C 1327-03. For each load value, 10 repeated measurements were performed, each with a dwell time of 10 s. The average hardness and standard deviation were determined.

The PBS (NaCl 8 g/L, KCl 0.2 g/L, Na₂HPO₄ 1.144 g/L, KH₂PO₄ 0.2 g/L, with a physiological pH of 7.4) immersion solution was used. Immersion time was 24 h. Sample size was 5 x 5 x 1 mm³.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Raw La₂O₃ powders show different shapes of the aggregates and particles (Fig. 1, Table 1).

XRD patterns of the pristine and added samples after SPS processing indicate formation of MgB₄ and MgO impurity phases (eq. 1-4). Oxygen is the residual one from the SPS chamber or from the adhered one on the raw powders. The XRD results also show the reaction between MgB₂ and addition, with formation of LaB₆ (Fig. 2). The average crystallite size (Table 2) of the pristine SPS-ed MgB₂ is similar to that of the raw MgB₂ powder (221 ± 83 nm), while for the added samples a decrease of MgB₂ crystallite size can be noticed. This is due to the reaction with the La₂O₃ additive. The average crystallite size from structural measurements (Williamson Hall analysis) is not reliable above 100-150 nm. Therefore, data from Table 2 should be accepted as qualitative.

Figure 1: Raw rare earth oxide powders: micro-La₂O₃ (a) and nano-La₂O₃ (b).

Raw material	Average Particle Size (APS), according to the supplier	Aggregate shape	Particle shape	Supplier	Purity (%)	Addition amount (wt.%)
MgB ₂	1-2 μm according to supplier (our SEM data show particles of 0.2-0.8 μm)	Cluster	Sphere like	Alfa Aesar	99,99	8,32
micro-La ₂ O ₃	100<DMP<200 nm	Coral like	Plate like	Chempur	99,9	8,32
nano-La ₂ O ₃	15-30 nm	Snow-flake like	Needle like	Alfa Aesar	99,99	8,32

Table 1: Some characteristics of the raw powders and their amount added into starting powder mixtures.

Figure 2: XRD patterns of the pristine MgB₂ powder (a), SPS-ed MgB₂ (b) and of the MgB₂ added with micro-La₂O₃ (c) and nano-La₂O₃ (d). Phase notation: (1) MgB₂, (2) MgO, (3) MgB₄, (4) LaB₆.

Pristine, micro- and nano-La₂O₃-added MgB₂ have close values of the apparent density (Table 2).

Sample	Phase	Crystallite size, D (nm)	MgO, (wt.%)	ρ_a (g/cm^3)
Pristine SPS-ed MgB_2	MgB_2	221 ± 83	7.3	2.52
MgB_2 + micro- La_2O_3	MgB_2	181 ± 156	6.77	2.63
	LaB_6	44 ± 3.5		
MgB_2 + nano- La_2O_3	MgB_2	151 ± 98	8.8	2.59
	LaB_6	46 ± 4.6		

Table 2: Some characteristics of the SPS-ed samples: crystallite size of MgB_2 and LaB_6 , MgO content, and measured apparent density (ρ_a).

SEM images taken on samples after SPS processing (Fig. 3) show a composite-like microstructure. A schematic drawing of the complex structure of added MgB_2 is shown in Fig. 4. The microstructure of added MgB_2 indicates that, during SPS, particles of MgB_2 form large relatively clean blocks, while newly formed secondary phases (MgO , MgB_4 , and LaB_6) mainly segregate around the clean MgB_2 blocks, generating a matrix-like region. The so-called clean MgB_2 blocks also contain fine secondary phases, but in a lower quantity (according to the EDS compositional maps, not shown here).

Figure 3: SEM images of (a) micro- La_2O_3 and (b) nano- La_2O_3 added MgB_2 , taken on fresh fractured surface. The left side of each image is taken in backscattering mode. In backscattering mode heavy elements (i.e. La) are detected as areas with a lighter (white) colour.

Figure 4: Schema of added MgB₂ microstructure.

The Vickers hardness (Fig. 5) was measured by indentation on clean blocks of MgB₂ and the values are more consistent than those taken on the matrix. Both types of La₂O₃ additions enhance the hardness of the added MgB₂, the highest influence being observed for the nano-La₂O₃ addition. The hardness values increase with the decrease of the applied load, as a result of the well-known indentation size effect.

Figure 5: Vickers hardness (HV) vs. indentation load of pristine and La₂O₃-added MgB₂ samples obtained by SPS.

The MgB₂ samples were immersed in PBS for 24 hours. The surface of the samples was covered by needles (Fig. 6). The EDS spectra on needles show the following composition: 4.7 wt. % (2.37 at. %) K, 5.72 wt. %, (4.91 at. %) Na, 19.48 wt. % (12.4 at. %) P, 1.33 wt. % (2.18 at. %) C, 53.07 wt. % (65.4 at. %) O, and 15.7 wt. % (12.74 at. %) Mg. No complex compound, consisting of all six elements was found in the XRD data base. Hence, a mixture of two or more compounds is expected to compose the needles. Within a rough approximation, the EDS and XRD data (Fig. 7) suggest formation of magnesium phosphate hydroxide (β -Mg₂PO₄OH, PDF#47-0957). Another phase likely to occur is sodium hydrogen phosphate hydrate (Na₃H₂P₃O₁₀·6H₂O, PDF #46-0121). We could not

identify in our XRD patterns K-containing compounds and we assume that K is a component element of the Mg and/or Na phosphates. Some carbon is present in our samples, perhaps due to the contamination from the graphite die used in the SPS processing.

Figure 6: SEM images of phosphate needles (see text) deposited on La_2O_3 -added MgB_2 samples.

Figure 7: XRD data for deposited layer on the La_2O_3 -added MgB_2 substrate. Phases are denoted with: 1 - $\text{Na}_3\text{H}_2\text{P}_3\text{O}_{10}\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 2 - $\text{Mg}_2\text{PO}_4\text{OH}$. Other peaks belongs to the substrate.

The observed phosphates are recognized as safe for human body, and all of them, at least as individual elements, can be found in the mineral composition of the bones. Although we have not performed a specific test, the adhesion quality of the deposited layer to the surface of MgB₂ samples is relatively good (although cleavage of the deposited layer occurs during sample manipulation).

The needles of phosphates were formed either scarcely (Fig. 6.a), or in rich regions radially distributed in dense bouquets (Fig. 6.b). At the present status of research it was not possible to have an understanding of the influence of the samples microstructure (strongly dependent on the La₂O₃ additive raw powder type) on the needles output, size, shape factor or agglomeration pattern. Needles have a ribbon-like or close to a cuboid-like (sometimes the transversal cross section is a rectangle or a parallelogram) filamentary shape (Fig. 6.c, d) with thickness of 100-700 nm, width of 0.5-5 μm and length up to 400 μm. The cuboid-like needles are usually larger in diameter than the ribbon-like ones and in some cases they are apparently formed of stacked ribbon-like filaments. The morphology of the needles is quite consistent with the monoclinic crystal structure of the Mg₂PO₄OH main phase.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Spark plasma sintering is a suitable technique for obtaining high density samples of MgB₂ added with La₂O₃.

Indentation properties of MgB₂ are improved by micro- or nano-La₂O₃ powder additives. A higher Vickers hardness is obtained for nano-La₂O₃ powder.

Our results suggest that deposition of phosphates on MgB₂ is feasible, indicating a presumptive bioactive surface. The role of the deposited layer can be also of a buffer, delaying the biodegradation of MgB₂ in human body. Further research is required to investigate the properties of the deposited layer and to conclude on the potential of MgB₂-RE₂O₃ composites for biomedical applications.

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